

Soil properties under monocropping and tree-based intercropping systems

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ABSTRACT

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*The agricultural systems influence soil properties. In this study two agricultural systems; 1) monocrop apple orchard with the use of synthetic fertilizer and 2) tree-based inter cropping (TBI) system fields, which were receiving both synthetic fertilizers and manure. Three fields of orchards and three TBI system fields were sampled. Soil analysis revealed that orchards in which no organic amendment was applied had 2 to 3-fold lower soil organic matter concentration than TBI system fields. The soil organic matter contents in orchards were 4.32, 2.9 and 3.41 g kg⁻¹; whereas, the soil organic matter contents of TBI system fields were 12.08, 14.77 and 17.93 g kg⁻¹. Moreover, one orchard field also had a potent root parasite; white grub cockchafer (*Phyllophaga* spp). The results of this study demonstrate that crop diversification as tree-based intercropping system and the use of manure along with synthetic fertilizer had a positive influence on soil property in terms of soil organic matter concentration.*

Introduction

Food demand is increasing day by day due to increasing population. World agriculture and land available for agriculture is getting limited with time due to increasing rate of urbanization and industrialization. On the other side, agricultural practices cause environmental issues such as

eutrophication and the emissions of potent greenhouse gases (nitrous oxide, methane and carbon dioxide) due to tillage practices and the use of synthetic fertilizers (Abdo et al., 2025; Gerke 2025). Scientists and policy makers are now seeking ways to reduce negative impact of agricultural practices on climate by proposing and implementing changes in agricultural management systems. The agricultural managements systems are divided into three main classes; conventional practices, conservation agriculture and organic

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agriculture (Aune, 2011). The conventional agriculture has hundreds of years of history since it involves the turning of soil (tillage) to avoid soil compaction ((Farooq and Siddiqui, 2015). With the passage of time after 1940s, new techniques were incorporated in this system; such as, the use of heavy machinery for deep tillage of soil (10 to 30 cm depth with mouldboard and chisel ploughing; (Chen et al., 2025; Irkiso et al., 2025), synthetic fertilizers and pesticides (Sumberg and Giller, 2022; Juyal, 2024). The green revolution, which began in 1940s and continued till 1970s, involved deforestation, extensive use of deep tillage, use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides to increase crop production, lead to soil quality deterioration (Patel, 2013). Deep tillage breaks soil aggregates, which exposes the organic matter to microorganisms to decompose (Liu et al., 2025). This leads to the reduction of soil organic matter (Srivastava, 2025). Soil organic matter plays central role in making organo-mineral complexes with clay and other mineral particles (sand and silt), making soil heavy and resistible against erosion (Gul et al., 2014; Bai et al., 2025). Conventional agriculture also involves the use of monocropping; however, the main characteristics of conventional agriculture is deep tillage and the use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides (Sumberg and Giller, 2022). Conservation agriculture idea stems from the catastrophe of Dust Bowl that happened in United States of America. This involved the massive dust storms in the Southern plans (Arkansas, Oklahoma, Texas, Kansas) of USA that started in 1930s and continued till 1940s (Hornbeck 2012; Holleman 2017). This catastrophe severely eroded the top soil layer of agricultural farms, leaving those lands uncultivable and forced the farmers to leave their hometowns and to migrate to other places (Hornbeck 2012). The idea of conservation agriculture (also known as sustainable agriculture) was proposed by Edward H. Faulkner (1945). According to Edward H. Faulkner (1945), in agricultural lands, shallow and less frequent, permanent soil cover with cover crops, mulching and residue return after crop harvest, more use of organic fertilizers (manure, compost) and less use of synthetic fertilizer (urea, NPK) was proposed. This management practice has found to be very effective in increasing the organic matter of soil and improves the soil aggregation (bigger and stronger aggregates) all across the world (Kassam et al., 2019). The organic agriculture is the one in which no synthetic fertilizer, no pesticide, no genetically modified crops and no tillage is applied (Aulakh et al., 2022). These agricultural practices have profound influence on soil quality. Conservation and organic agriculture improve soil quality significantly relative to conventional agriculture. Conservation and organic agriculture increase soil organic matter contents, the concentration of nutrients, promote the

formation of bigger and stronger soil aggregates and increase soil biodiversity for mesofauna and macrofauna (Christel et al., 2021; Sofo et al., 2022; Mamabolo et al., 2024).

Tobab Kakri is a small town of Balochistan, near Qandahar border. It is a cold-winter dessert. The local people of this region are mostly connected with farming. However, till date no data is available about soil quality under various farming systems. In this study, two contrasting farming systems were considered; (1) orchards under monocropping and inorganic fertilizer management (type of conventional farming system) and diversified cropping system with trees and crops cultivated together (conservation agriculture due to diversified cropping system). The soil organic matter contents, pH, electrical conductivity, soil texture (concentrations of clay, silt and sand) and the types and abundances of soil macrofauna. The hypothesis of this study was; monocroping and the use of synthetic fertilizers reduces SOM contents and the abundances of soil macrofauna and soil mesofauna relative to the diversified cropping system.

Material and Method

Area of study (Toba Kakri)

Current research work was conducted in 2024 in area of Toba Kakri (31°02' N, 67. °46' E) within district Pishin Balochistan Pakistan. The experimental site was located near Barshore subdivision of district Pishin in south of Balochistan. It is a cold-winter desert that receives snowfall in winter and the winter temperature occasionally drops below -15°C. The cumulative rainfall and the average minimum and maximum temperature data of this region are provided in the Table 1.

Table 1. Monthly cumulative rainfall (mm) and average minimum and maximum temperature of Toba Kakri during 2024.

Month	Rainfall (mm)	Minimum temperature (°C)	Maximum temperature (°C)
January	2.3	3.58	14.45
February	9.9	3.93	14
March	22.1	8.8	17.74
April	28.5	12.76	21.9
May	1.9	20.32	32.09
June	2.4	23.54	34.81
July	29.4	25.67	35.03
August	27.8	23	30.83
September	4.3	21.5	31.73
October	1.3	16.16	27.25
November	0	10.6	23.03
December	0	1.87	13.09

Three orchard and three tree-based intercropping (TBI) system fields were selected for this study. The farmers of each field were asked about the age of field, cropping system, type of tillage practice and type of fertilizers applied in field.

Figure 1. Study fields. O-F; orchard field, T-F; tree-based intercropping (TBI) field, 1, 2, 3; number of field sites.

Collection of soil sample and their Analysis

In each selected field site, soil was collected from five locations by using the random walk method. With the help of a corer, which was 10 cm in height and 5 cm in diameter, soil was collected from the depth of 0-10 cm. Soil samples after collection, were put over a sheet of clean paper to collect any visible soil fauna in a plastic bottle of 50 ml capacity and with 2.5 diameter opening size. The samples of soil were thereafter collected in labeled zip-lock plastic bags and were brought to laboratory. The soil samples were left open to air dry and after air drying, they were passed through a 2 mm mesh sieve to remove stones and other big particles. The pH and electrical conductivity of soil samples were measured after making a paste of soil by adding 20 ml of water into 10 g soil in a labeled beaker. Soil texture and soil organic matter were also analyzed. Soil organic matter was measured with Walkley-Black method. The manual of Estefan et al. (2013) was used for all soil physical (texture) and chemical (pH, E and soil organic matter) properties.

Soil fauna

The fauna that was found in soil samples were collected as The pH of soils of orchard fields were 7.85, 8.36 and 8.35. The electrical conductivity of soils of orchard fields were 0.27, 3.20 and 0.45 dS m⁻¹. The pH of soils of TBI system fields were 8.41, 8.15 and 8.32. The EC of soils of TBI system fields were 0.42, 0.40 and 0.66 dS m⁻¹ (Figure 2). The soil textures of these fields were sandy to sandy loam (Figure 2). The soil organic matter was significantly higher in TBI system fields than orchards (Figure 2; P<0.05). The soil organic matter contents contents of orchard fields were 4.32, 2.9 and 3.41 g kg⁻¹. The soil organic matter contents of TBI system fields were 12.08, 14.77 and 17.93 (Figure well as any soil fauna that was found under the range of eye site from the

point of soil collection was also collected. The pictures of butterfly and ants were taken as they could not be collected.

Statistical Analysis

The differences in the soil organic matter contents between field sites were calculated with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and least significance difference (LSD) tests. Microsoft Excel and Costate software's were used for statistical analysis and graphs.

Results

Apple trees were grown in all selected orchard fields as a monocrop. The orchards were of 10, 15 and 37 years of age. All orchard fields were under the same management practice. Synthetic fertilizer (NPK) was used and pesticides were applied once every year (Table 2). The tree-based intercropping (TBI) system fields were 3, 15 and 2 years old. These TBI systems were grown on abandoned lands, which were orchard fields before 2004. Due to long drought (from 1996 till 2004), farmers cut those orchards and left the lands barren. These lands are now re-cultivated.

Table 1. Age (years), tillage systems, cropping systems and fertilizer management systems of agricultural field sites selected for this study.

Field site	Age (years) ¹	Tillage practice	Crops	Fertilizers
O-F1	Ten	Manual tillage with spade (shallow)	Apple	Synthetic fertilizer (Nitro Phos), pesticides, removal of residues (tree twigs after pruning)
O-F2	Fifteen	Manual tillage with spade (shallow)	Apple	Synthetic fertilizer (Nitro Phos), pesticides, removal of residues (tree twigs after pruning)
O-F3	Thirty seven	Manual tillage with spade (shallow)	Apple	Synthetic fertilizer (Nitro Phos), pesticides, removal of residues (tree twigs after pruning)
T-1	Three	Tillage with machine (deep) for crops and shallow tillage under trees	Apple and tomato	Synthetic fertilizer (Nitro Phos), pesticides, removal of residues (tree twigs and after pruning and crop residues after harvest)
T-2	Fifteen	Tillage with machine (deep) for crops and shallow tillage under trees	Apple and Tomatto	Synthetic fertilizer (nitro phos), manure, pesticides, residue removal from tree pruning and vegetable harvest
T-3	Two	Tillage with machine (deep) for crops and shallow tillage under trees	Apple and medicago	Synthetic fertilizer (Nitro Phos), pesticides, removal of residues (tree twigs and after pruning and crop residues after harvest)

¹Orchards and TBI-F1 were planted on uncultivated barren soil, croplands were cultivated on abandoned lands that were lush green orchards before drought period of 8 years (from 1996 to 2004). ²Deep tillage of soil cultivated with vegetables and shallow of soil cultivated with trees. O-F; orchard field, T-F; tree-based intercropping (TBI) field, 1, 2, 3; number of field sites. 2).

Figure 2. The pH, electrical conductivity (EC dS m⁻¹), texture (clay, silt and sand contents as g kg⁻¹) and soil organic matter contents (g kg⁻¹) of soils of study field sites. O-F; orchard field, T-F; tree-based intercropping (TBI) field, 1, 2, 3; number of field sites.

Soil fauna

Total ten soil mesofauna and macrofauna were found. They were small black ant (*Camponotus compressus*), ant with big head and black color (*Vermessor pergandei*), white grub cockchafer (*Phyllophaga spp*), black-dotted white butterfly (*Pieris rapae*), black-dotted orange butterfly (*Danaus chrysippus*), earthworm (*Ascaris lumbricoides*), *Coccinella septempunctata* (lady bird beetle), giant spider (*Heteropoda venatoria*), black spider (*Paradosa timidula*), large-size ant with red head *Cataglyphis nodus* (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Soil mesofauna and macrofauna found in study field sites. The small black ant *Camponotus compressus* was the

most common mesofauna found in almost all fields (except T-F1 and T-F2). The two butterfly species black-dotted white butterfly (*Pieris rapae*), black-dotted orange butterfly (*Danaus chrysippus*) were found in all study fields except T-F1 (Table 3). The number of soil fauna species was higher in orchards than TBI system fields (Table 3).

Table 3. Number of soil macro fauna species, species types and number of individuals of each species from a given agro ecosystem of Toba Kakri, Balochistan, Pakistan.

Sampling site	Number of soil fauna species	Types of soil fauna	Number of individuals
-F1	5	Small black ant (<i>Camponotus compressus</i>)	Innumerable
		Ant with big head and black color (<i>Vermessor pergandei</i>)	Innumerable
		White grub cockchafer (<i>Phyllophaga spp</i>)	4
		Black-dotted white butterfly (<i>Pieris rapae</i>) Black-dotted orange butterfly (<i>Danaus chrysippus</i>)	Uncountable Uncountable
-F2	5	Small black ant (<i>Camponotus compressus</i>)	Innumerable
		<i>Cataglyphis nodus</i> Earthworm (<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>)	Innumerable 2
		Black-dotted white butterfly (<i>Pieris rapae</i>) Black-dotted orange butterfly (<i>Danaus chrysippus</i>)	Uncountable Uncountable
-F3	5	Small black ant (<i>Camponotus compressus</i>)	Innumerable
		Red ant with black head and tail (<i>Camponotus consobrinus</i>)	Innumerable
		Lady bug (<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i>)	2
		<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i> (lady bird beetle)	1
		Black-dotted white butterfly <i>Pieris rapae</i> Black-dotted orange butterfly <i>Danaus chrysippus</i>	Uncountable Uncountable
-F1	1	Wood louse (<i>Porcellio scaber</i>)	3
-F2	4	Big ant with maroon head (<i>Cataglyphis nodus</i>)	Innumerable
		Giant spider (<i>Heteropoda venatoria</i>) Black-dotted orange butterfly <i>Danaus chrysippus</i> Black-dotted white butterfly <i>Pieris rapae</i>	1 Uncountable Uncountable
-F3	3	Small black ant (<i>Camponotus compressus</i>) Earthworm (<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>) Black spider (<i>Paradosa timidula</i>)	Innumerable 3 1

O-F; orchard field, T-F; tree-based intercropping (TBI) field, 1, 2, 3; number of field sites.

Discussion

The study field sites were of two types; apple orchards and TBI system fields. The apple orchards were of different ages; however, all of them were receiving inorganic fertilizer. Shallow tillage was applied once in every year. Furthermore, after pruning of trees, the twigs were removed. The non-application of organic fertilizers (manure, compost, tree twig residues), shallow tillage and the continuous use of inorganic fertilizers may explain very low soil organic matter contents. No application of organic fertilizers reduces the soil organic matter contents (Raffa et al., 2015; Alvarez et al., 2024; Yuan et al., 2025). In contrast, the TBI systems had several-fold higher soil organic matter than orchards (4.32, 2.9 and 3.41 g kg⁻¹ in orchards versus 12.08, 14.77 and 17.93 in TBI system fields). The TBI system fields were regrown on abandoned lands that were once fertile orchards before 1996. Due to long

drought spell from 1996 and 2004 and the severe shortage of electricity, which was required for irrigation, those orchards were destroyed. After the availability of solar system, farmers have re-cultivated those abandoned lands, which might had high soil organic matter concentrations. This may explain that despite of only two and three years of TBI system, soil had several-fold higher soil organic matter than orchard fields. In TBI systems, farmers grow crops in between trees. Furthermore, they also apply manure (obtained from the farms of buffalo and cow). This crop diversification, the amendment of manure and shallow tillage may also explain several-fold higher soil organic matter concentrations in these fields as compared to monocrop apple orchards. The growing of crops in between trees offers more soil organic matter addition in soil than monocropping. The crops underneath trees cover soil surface and add organic matter in soil. The vegetables, cereals or pulses in orchards act as cover crops. Crop diversification is known for promoting the accrual of soil organic matter by improving soil microbial activities (Gul and Whalen, 2022; Zayani et al., 2025).

Despite of high soil organic matter in TBI system fields, the number of species of soil fauna was less in these fields. This may be due to the young age of these fields than orchards. Another finding was the presence of white grub cockchafer (*Phyllophaga* spp) in orchard field 1. This larva is a potent plant root parasite that can enter up to 45 cm depth in drought and cold conditions (McColloch, 1923). Since the soil sampling was conducted in April, the weather was still very cold. Therefore, this macrofauna was not found in other orchard fields. However, according to the local farmers, this parasite was also observed in other orchards in which inorganic fertilizers were applied. More research is required to study if these parasites are also present in soil with high soil organic matter. The use of pesticides to reduce the adverse effect of these parasites on roots of trees, may adversely influence soil quality.

Conclusions

This research attempted to find out the influence of two different cropping systems on soil organic matter contents and soil fauna; monocrop orchards receiving only inorganic fertilizers and pesticides versus diversified tree-based intercropping (TBI) systems, which were receiving manure along with synthetic fertilizers. The results showed that compared to orchards the soil under TBI system fields had several-fold higher organic matter contents. However, despite of this high concentration, these soils had low number of species of soil macrofauna. This study provides important information for the farmers that TBI systems are more favorable for soil quality and the use of manures need to be promoted to increase the soil organic matter contents.

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